

D6.7 - Lessons learned in VitiGEOSS for climate services and Earth observations communities

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-SC5-2019-2 GA No. 869565
Project title	Vineyard Innovative Tool based on the InteGration of Earth Observation Services and in-field Sensors
Duration of the project	September 2020 - February 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP6
Document due Date:	10/11/2023
Actual date of delivery	10/11/2023
Leader of this deliverable	BSC
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Submitted

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869565. This website reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
V1	27 October 2023	Andria Nicodemou (BSC)	First draft circulated to partners
	7 November 2023	Federico Oldani (LINKS), Tommaso Monopoli (LINKS), Jessica Snoek (eLEAF), Marta Terrado (BSC), Nuria Perez-Zanon (BSC)	Contributions and revisions added
V2	10 November 2023	Andria Nicodemou (BSC)	Final document

Executive summary

This deliverable provides a summary of some of the key insights and lessons learned during the project that could serve as added knowledge for the climate services and Earth observations communities.

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1. Introduction

VitiGEOSS is a 42-month H2020-funded project aiming to promote the use of European open Earth observation (EO) services and develop an innovative vineyard management tool based on the integration of EO, and in-field sensors to increase the resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to the viticulture sector.

The project responds to future challenges of the worldwide food and wine industry, which include the need to intensify the production in a sustainable way, mitigate the effects of climate change, reduce negative environmental externalities and promote local economic growth.

This deliverable provides a summary of several lessons learned during the project that could serve as added knowledge for the climate services and EO communities in their interactions with users, to ensure the provision of understandable and useful information.

2. Climate services and Earth observations in VitiGEOSS

As part of the VitiGEOSS project, research was conducted in the fields of climate services and EO. The VitiGEOSS platform – the main outcome of the project – provides a single entry-point of information tailored to the needs of wine producers, with the aim to assist in better vineyard management and sustainability. The platform makes use of climate information and European EO to provide information on weather and climate, phenology, crop status, disease, and business and sustainability management.

Climate services refer to the provision of scientifically credible climate information that can be applied in decision making. “The service component involves a demand-driven approach, appropriate engagement with the decision makers, an effective access mechanism and responsiveness to user needs”, as defined by the project *Climateurope2* (Zorita et al., 2023). In VitiGEOSS, climate predictions at the sub-seasonal and seasonal timescales were provided to the three end-users involved in the project (wine producers based in Spain, Italy and Portugal). These predictions were developed through a co-production approach to ensure that they are tailored to the specific needs of the end-users and provide clear and understandable information.

Earth observation (EO) refers to the “use of remote sensing technologies to monitor land, marine (seas, rivers, lakes) and atmosphere”¹. In VitiGEOSS, satellite data (e.g., Copernicus Sentinel-2), drone images, and in-situ measurements through sensors were used to produce useful crop status indicators (such as evapotranspiration, biomass production and crop water demand), as well as forecasts of the phenological stages. This information supports more efficient and better field management and planning.

Throughout the VitiGEOSS project, partners have actively engaged and exchanged knowledge with the broader climate services and EO communities. For instance, a webinar was organised focusing on the climate predictions developed in the project, presented during a *Climateurope2* webstival, a European project bringing together the climate services community. Another webinar, held as a side event at the EU Green Week, focused on remote sensing data for vineyard monitoring, and attracted researchers, technology providers and other stakeholders from the EO community. Other notable interactions included the collaboration and participation in a workshop of the European project *e-Shape*, bringing together key actors in the EO field. This was carried out during the initial stages of the intelligent services’ design in VitiGEOSS, and helped shape these services. Additionally, VitiGEOSS held a participatory workshop during the EuroGEO 2023 conference, presenting the research, outcomes and knowledge acquired during the project to the EO community, and encouraging

¹ EUSPA - European Union Agency for the Space Programme [[link](#)]

discussion on the value and future applications of this research. Further interactions with these two communities were achieved through the participation in targeted conferences and other events.

3. Lessons learned

The climate services and EO research in VitiGEOSS built on existing knowledge, such as experiences from past EU-funded projects preceding VitiGEOSS (e.g. VISCA, MED-GOLD, Climateurope), while it also drew from current projects and initiatives, such as Climateurope2, ASPECT, e-Shape and EuroGEO. The project established routes for interacting with important actors in the climate services and EO communities to exchange knowledge, as well as with relevant stakeholders (like potential users or providers of services).

Overall, the research and user engagement in VitiGEOSS allowed to obtain valuable feedback to improve the services offered in the project platform, while at the same time, the insights and knowledge generated can benefit the climate services and EO communities, and eventually end-users of the services (i.e. wine producers).

This deliverable delves into certain key lessons learned in the project, which are considered crucial in the development of these services and can help guide future interactions among researchers (climate and data scientists), technology providers and potential users, ensuring the production and delivery of clear, useful, usable, tailored and scalable information. This added knowledge can help find common ground in terms of expectations, needs and language.

It should be noted that the knowledge gained in the project is not limited to the points discussed in this deliverable, however these were selected as important insights contributing to the legacy of the project, and inspiring for future research and applications in the climate services and EO realms.

The lessons learned described in the subsequent sections are:

- Users can benefit from a single platform providing multiple services
- Co-production is essential for useful and usable information
- Integrating scientific and sectoral knowledge is necessary for effective services
- Building capacity among end-users is key for services' uptake
- Remote sensing can be a good and affordable option to obtain information for vineyard monitoring tasks
- Balancing data sharing and privacy of sensitive information is important
- Services should be designed to be potentially scalable

3.1 Users can benefit from a single platform providing multiple services

Challenge: A wide range of information is required for effective vineyard management and decision making, ranging from information on meteorological and climate conditions to crop status and diseases. However, this information is typically provided through separate services.

Solution: A single platform that integrates several intelligent services, tailored to the needs of wine producers, is ideal for obtaining all the needed information from one source.

In viticulture, information on weather, climate, phenology, diseases, and crop status is essential for effective and sustainable vineyard management, and to support strategic and operational decisions. However, wine producers and viticulturists typically have to obtain this information from different sources and tools. This can be time-consuming, costly (as purchasing several services might be needed) and challenging, as it may require advanced expertise to use different tools and interpret information presented in diverse manners and formats.

One of the main aims of the VitiGEOSS project was to develop an “one-stop shop” that integrates the essential information required for vineyard management, to ultimately enable more sustainable viticultural practices.

VitiGEOSS, building on and improving previous research outputs and tools focused on the wine sector and agriculture (such as from European projects and initiatives like VISCA and MED-GOLD, as well as tools like FruitLook, among others), has developed tailored services that combine data from multiple sources and provide them within a **single platform**. The data sources include satellites, weather stations, climate models, fixed cameras, in-field technologies, and end-user information. The [VitiGEOSS platform](#) integrates five intelligent services, providing weather and climate predictions, phenological status information, crop status indicators, disease management information, and a business and sustainability service.

This platform provides users access to all this information, tailored to their specific location and fields, without needing to use multiple platforms and tools, thus allowing them to more effectively manage and optimise their vineyard operations, ultimately leading to cost reduction and more sustainable practices.

Figure 1. VitiGEOSS platform, with different services shown under the “Analyse” menu.

3.2 Co-production is essential for useful and usable information

Challenge: A service can often lack the capacity to respond to the specific user needs, as it is not tailored to their requirements. This can be due to a mismatch between the information needed to support users’ decisions and aspects, such as the range of information provided, its timeliness, and even the way this information is displayed or delivered to the intended users, which can affect the understanding of this information and therefore its application.

Solution: To overcome this gap between research and useful operational services, a co-production approach allows scientists to interact with users throughout the development process to better design and tailor such services to user needs.

A **co-production approach** creates a space where scientists and users interact, allowing them to closely collaborate and develop together services and information that are fit-for-purpose, clear, usable and scalable (Terrado et al., 2023).

In VitiGEOSS, the consortium followed **user-centred design** processes throughout the project duration, placing the end users of the intelligent services at the centre of the platform design and development process. Three wine producing companies based in different regions – namely Mastroberardino from Italy, Symington from Portugal and Torres from Spain – participated as users and partners in the VitiGEOSS project. This allowed for their active and direct involvement, and contribution to all the project activities and research. By sharing their perspective, knowledge and experiences, researchers and users were able to find common ground and learn from each other, while ensuring the usefulness and usability of the VitiGEOSS services.

The user-centred design approach used in VitiGEOSS, iterations with users and their outcomes have been described extensively in previous project deliverables, such as Deliverables 2.1 and 3.1. The process is summarised in Figure 2 (see D2.1 for more details).

Figure 2. Summary of the main aspects of the approach followed in VitiGEOSS (adapted from VitiGEOSS Deliverable 2.1; source: ISO 13407, ISO9241:210).

VitiGEOSS has worked to:

- define use cases and identify the specific needs of the users to offer the best user experience to grape growers on using the intelligent services for weather and climate, phenology, key crop indicators, disease management and business and sustainability,
- co-design the look and information included in the intelligent services,
- adapt the services according to the user needs through multiple feedback cycles, and
- evaluate how users interacted with the information provided and applied it in their activities and decision-making processes.

How was co-production achieved in VitiGEOSS?

There were several iterations during the project lifetime, beginning as early as the first months of the project. Some of these iterations included:

- Group and individual meetings with users from early on in the project to understand their needs and explain important concepts behind the services/research
- Knowledge exchange with other past and current projects to feed into the co-design activities of the project, such as:
 - Exchanges and participation in a workshop organised by [e-shape](#) during the early phases of VitiGEOSS to share experiences in the co-design of EO services
 - Interactions with the climate services community and learning from other projects and initiatives, such as [Climateurope2](#), [ASPECT](#) and [MED-GOLD](#).
- Several rounds of interviews with end users for data / feedback collection
 - Initial interviews with individual users to discuss the first mock-ups of the services.
 - Implementation of feedback, and several further interactions with users to define subsequent versions of the mock-ups and discuss their functionality.
- Online survey for end-users, and later extension to external stakeholders, to collect their specific information requirements
- Monthly follow-up meetings to solve any doubts and evaluate the use of services
- Internal workshops (e.g. during the project's General Assembly) where users could share their experiences and knowledge on decision making using the VitiGEOSS services

Co-production and the abovementioned actions formed an integral part of all services but were a particularly important part of the development of the climate services displayed in the VitiGEOSS platform. Building on knowledge from previous projects developing sub-seasonal and seasonal predictions (such as [S2S4E](#)) and the co-production framework for climate services by Bojovic et al. (2021), the team at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center developed a product that users found easy to understand and use.

In particular, aspects related to the visualisation of the climate forecasts were co-designed with users to ensure their ease-of-use, such as: the colours used to depict normal, above normal and below normal forecasts according to each variable; manner in which climate extremes were displayed; the presentation of skill etc. Some of the visualisations shared during the co-production process are shown in Figure 3, while the final version is shown in Figure 4.

The co-production behind these forecasts and lessons learned throughout the operationalisation process are discussed in detail in a forthcoming paper by Pérez-Zanón et al. (to be submitted). The paper includes an illustration of how intermediary users incorporate climate services outputs in their impact models and how end-users can make decisions based on the information provided.

TERCILES PROBABILITIES

Figure 3. Examples of initial mock-ups of climate services shared with users on how tercile probabilities, skill and extremes are displayed (more information in D3.1; images displayed as Figures 10-12 in the deliverable).

Figure 4. Final visualisation of climate forecasts, after integration of user feedback.

3.3 Integrating scientific and sectoral knowledge is necessary for effective services

Challenge: Wine producers and other users of climate and EO information are not scientists and might not have the expertise to interpret this information. On the other hand, climate and data scientists do not have extensive sectoral knowledge to allow for selecting the information to deliver that would be most appropriate for decision making. There is a need to create a new type of knowledge that integrate scientists’ and practitioners’ knowledge.

Solution: VitiGEOSS has strived to bring together scientists and viticulture stakeholders through a wide range of activities, events and interactions, in order to exchange knowledge and create a space for learning and collaborating.

Wine producers, viticulturists, farmers and vineyard managers are some of the potential users of the VitiGEOSS platform and its intelligent services. These stakeholders have extensive knowledge of the wine sector, such as the challenges faced on a daily basis (e.g., extreme weather events, disease management, decisions on irrigation), as well as the future challenges resulting from the changing climate (e.g., deciding on appropriate grape varieties based on future conditions, assessing the future water needs). Some of the decisions that wine producers might need to make in relation to different timescales are displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Examples of decisions viticulturists might face at different timescales.

Having the trustworthy information to inform decision-making is essential. However, researchers in the climate services and EO fields might not necessarily have the expertise to determine the exact type of information needed (e.g., which indicators might be more useful for wine producers to make specific decisions), or how this information should be expressed to be quickly and effectively understood by farmers.

VitiGEOSS has worked to bridge the gap between science and sectoral knowledge by creating spaces for researchers and wine producers to come together, exchange knowledge, share experiences and find common ground in terms of needs, expectations and language (referring to both the terminology used and the language barrier). This was achieved through several activities, such as the local stakeholder sessions.

Regarding finding common ground, the co-production approach (described earlier in more detail) allowed climate and EO researchers to interact directly with the end users and determine how to simplify and adapt the terminology used and information provided to make it more accessible, easy-to-use and understandable (for example, how probabilistic climate information is expressed). This

ensures that tools like the VitiGEOSS platform are useful and useable, even to new users, considering that minimal training is provided. The project ensured that continuous learning and knowledge-sharing opportunities were present for both sides throughout the co-production process: wine producers could express any doubts during regular meetings and learn during dedicated sessions to explain the science behind the tools (e.g., training on how to interpret climate forecasts), while technical partners could improve their services through the continuous user feedback.

How was knowledge exchange achieved in VitiGEOSS?

The project organised and participated in a wide variety of activities and events where interactions between sectoral actors and researchers were made possible. These included the following:

- **Technical webinars:** A webinar series was organised during the project, which brought together viticulture and agriculture stakeholders, technology and service providers, and the scientific community, in particular climate services and EO researchers. These explained the technical aspects behind the VitiGEOSS services, cover topics such as climate predictions, remote sensing and EO. In addition, one of the sessions was held during the Climateurope2 webstival, bringing together climate services stakeholders and the wine sector community. The webinars built a basis for the users to better understand the services and how to interpret the information given. They also provided an opportunity for researchers to interact with potential users outside of those involved in the project and showcase how climate services, EO and other services could help support decision making for better and more sustainable vineyard management and agricultural practices.
- **Local Stakeholder Sessions:** Three sessions were held during the project, targeting stakeholders in the three regions where the end-users involved in the project are based: Spain, Italy and Portugal. The first session (Spanish) was held online due to the pandemic, while the following two hybrid sessions were held at the facilities of the project end users in Italy and Portugal. A total of 240+ attendees participated in these sessions. The aim of the sessions was to reach stakeholders in their local language, inform them about tools such as those developed in the project, and build capacity in terms of the application of these tools for more sustainable agriculture.
- **Participatory workshops:** Two workshops were held: one with a more ‘commercial’ nature as it was held at [Enoforum](#) in May 2023, a large technical-scientific conference attracting many professionals in the viticulture sector; and the other with a purpose of bringing insights from the project to the EO research community at the [EuroGEO 2023](#) conference in October 2023. The first participatory workshop enabled direct interaction with potential users of tools like the VitiGEOSS platform, obtaining valuable feedback on the services presented, as well as educating potential future users. During the second participatory workshop, VitiGEOSS researchers brought to the EO community important insights from their interactions with viticulturists throughout the project, which could serve to improve tools and services of the future.

3.4 Building capacity among end-users is key for services' uptake

Challenge: *Information like climate forecasts and crop indicators can be technical and challenging to interpret and use in decision making for end users without the necessary training and knowledge. Providing resources and building capacity among end-users is essential to ensure that the services provided are useful and usable.*

Solution: *VitiGEOSS ensured that adequate training sessions and interactions with users were carried out so that users understood the information provided and could make use of it in their operations.*

End users have advanced expertise in their sector, and obtaining and using this expertise can help researchers develop a service that is better tailored to their needs, as discussed earlier. However, some users might lack the technical background and knowledge to interpret complicated concepts, such as different aspects of climate predictions (e.g. probabilities, skill etc.). Adapting the language used in the interactions of scientists with users and the way complex concepts are expressed in the services provided is only one step in the right direction. Building capacity is a critical aspect in making a service useful and usable, so that it can serve a meaningful purpose in informing the users' operations and decisions.

Capacity building played an important role in VitiGEOSS, as we strived to provide the project's end users and other potential users within the viticulture sector the necessary capabilities to understand, interpret and use the information provided through the VitiGEOSS platform.

Climate researchers ensured that adequate "training" and interactions with the project end users were carried out to clarify concepts behind climate forecasts and how to interpret them, for example: their distinction from weather forecasts, explanation of the probabilistic nature of the climate forecasts, how to interpret skill and extremes, and use these in decision making, etc. These interactions included individual and group meetings and workshops that were carried out throughout the project, as well as providing resources like a user guide on climate forecasts, shared with the users early in the project, when the forecasts were first made available.

Other opportunities for capacity building included the development of material (such as informational sheets) and instructional videos on the different intelligent services provided in the VitiGEOSS platform. In addition, activities like the technical webinars delved into technical background behind the different services, providing the project's end users along with other interested actors from the viticulture sector the necessary tools to better understand the forecasts, indicators and information presented in the platform.

3.5 Remote sensing can be a good and affordable option to obtain information for vineyard monitoring tasks

Challenge: *Wine producers require near real-time information on the vineyard's status in order to plan ahead and manage their operations effectively. Acquiring such information traditionally requires in person field surveys by the viticulturists or gathering data from in-field sensors scattered throughout the vineyard. Both approaches are often time-consuming and expensive to conduct on a regular basis.*

Solution: *By using satellite imagery to analyse the vineyard, VitiGEOSS provides wine producers with valuable data on the phenology and health status of their crops that is much more frequent and affordable to obtain, helping to save money and resources, and improve vineyard sustainability.*

In viticulture, it is critical to carefully monitor the growth process and health conditions of the grapevines to ensure that essential vineyard operations (e.g. irrigation, fertilisation, pruning, disease control, removal of spontaneous groundcover vegetation, and harvesting) are carried out at the right time, only where required and in a timely manner. This requires information on the vineyard and crop status to be acquired on a regular basis, which can be difficult, time-consuming and costly to obtain.

Traditionally, viticulturists gather valuable information by manually inspecting the grapevines, conducting in person vineyard surveys on a regular basis. This approach is effective as an experienced viticulturist knows how to observe and study grapevines in order to recognize and extract valuable information on their status and rapidly take informed decisions about vineyard management. However, this approach is clearly not feasible for very large vineyard estates, as it would be too time consuming to conduct on a regular basis.

Another way to acquire valuable data is installing in-field sensors throughout the vineyard, such as weather stations, hygrometers, soil nutrient and pH sensors, temperature sensors, in-field cameras, frost alarms, disease and pest monitoring systems and much more. These systems have the advantage of providing frequent, precise and punctual information on the grapevines' health and growth process. On the other hand, it is usually required to install a high number of these sensors throughout the field to have a complete overview of the vineyard status. For this reason, this approach can easily get too expensive even for medium-sized vineyards, considering the installation and maintenance costs of the sensors.

In recent years, remote sensing techniques have become increasingly pervasive in the field of precision agriculture, as they overcome the main disadvantages of manual and proximal sensing monitoring approaches discussed so far. In fact, remote sensing data sources, such as satellites, are easily scalable with the vineyard size, as they can capture multispectral views of an entire vineyard with a single flyover. This data can be used for downstream monitoring tasks, such as the computation of biophysical quantities and vegetation indexes to assess the health status of the grapevines. Non-commercial satellite data (e.g. ESA Copernicus Sentinel satellites) holds particular relevance, as it is provided for free and is readily available online. The main drawback of using satellites is their resolution and revisit time; moreover, optical satellites can be exploited only in good weather conditions. For example, the optical satellite Sentinel-2 has an average revisit time of 5 days and a spatial resolution of 10 m/px. For more fine-grained monitoring tasks, satellite data can be supported with other remote sensing data sources having a higher resolution. Camera drones are well-suited for this kind of tasks, as they exhibit a resolution of a few cm/px, even though performing drone surveys has moderate costs and is feasible only for small/medium-sized vineyards.

In the VitiGEOSS platform, remote sensing data from non-commercial satellites form the basis for the provision of crop status indicators. The key crop indicators support the users with weekly information

on growth-related biophysical quantities, such as evapotranspiration levels, biomass production, nitrogen content, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Leaf Area Index (LAI) and more. An example of an NDVI time-series analysis for a sample vineyard is visualized in Figure 6.

Figure 6. An example of an average NDVI time-series analysis on a sample vineyard (Familia Torres's Agrolab).

Satellite data also powers a phenological monitoring service offered by the VitiGEOSS platform. This service is based on an artificial intelligence model capable of estimate the current phenological stage (according to the Baggioini scale) of the grapevines in the vineyard from Sentinel-3 time-series temperature data. Despite its low resolution of 1 km/px, Sentinel-3 data was successfully exploited to monitor phenology with a mean absolute error of just 6 days.

Figure 7. Data and models used to produce the phenology service in VitiGEOSS.

In conclusion, a valuable lesson learned from the VitiGEOSS project is that remote sensing data can be the best and most affordable option for many vineyard monitoring tasks. In particular, satellite data is well suited for those tasks not requiring high resolution data (e.g. phenological monitoring with Sentinel-3, NDVI analysis with Sentinel-2), even more so for large vineyards, which are difficult to monitor with other approaches due to their size. For more fine-grained monitoring tasks (i.e., at a vineyard row scale) satellite data can be supported by drone-acquired data or by very high resolution commercial satellite data, which is deemed to be more expensive to acquire and suitable only for monitoring small (parts of the) vineyards.

3.6 Balancing data sharing and privacy of sensitive information is important

Challenge: *Ground data in viticulture, including private weather station data and in-field observations, lacks open and homogeneous formats, hindering the development of new services. Growers are often unwilling to share sensitive information about their fields due to the labour-intensive nature of vineyards and the time invested in data collection.*

Solution: *The VitiGEOSS project is proposing a two-fold strategy to address this challenge. First, transparency is ensured by publishing certain datasets, such as those from the in-field camera and drone services. Second, for data that must remain private, the project ensures that metadata is openly accessible, facilitating collaboration by connecting interested users with data owners while preserving the privacy of sensitive information. This approach strikes a balance between open-source data and the protection of growers' proprietary knowledge in viticulture.*

In the ever-evolving realm of agriculture, access to data is indispensable for growth, innovation, and sustainable practices. The use of open-source satellite imagery has undoubtedly been a game-changer, providing valuable insights into our fields and vineyards. Global open data can allow the portability of some services to other regions, among other benefits. However, the landscape becomes more complex when we consider ground data from private weather stations and in-field observations, particularly in viticulture, where vineyards are often closely guarded treasures.

A notable challenge we encounter is the scarcity of open accessible ground data. Unlike satellite imagery, which is readily available in open-source formats, the data from private weather stations and in-field observations often lacks uniformity, making it challenging to integrate and develop new services effectively. For instance, the measurement scales for phenology can vary widely, leading to discrepancies in data interpretation.

The primary reason behind this disparity lies in the nature of the data and the attitudes of those who collect it. Wine growers are often hesitant to share sensitive information about their fields, and their concerns are entirely valid. In-field data often represents years of significant investment of time and intricate knowledge, making it impractical for many growers to contribute data openly.

In the VitiGEOSS project, we strive to strike a balance between addressing the need for open data and respecting the growers' concerns. To achieve this, the following two-fold strategy is suggested:

First, transparency can be ensured by making our work and data publicly available, especially when it comes to certain services, such as the in-field cameras and drone services. These datasets will be published, providing a valuable resource to the wider community.

Second, where data privacy is paramount, we will maintain the data as private, but we will ensure that the metadata is openly accessible. This approach allows interested users to connect with the data owners directly, thereby fostering collaboration while preserving the sensitivity of the information.

In the quest for progress and innovation in viticulture, striking a balance between open-source data and the protection of proprietary knowledge is crucial. By making certain data open and transparent, we can collectively advance our understanding and practices in the field, while still respecting the growers' rightful concerns about their vineyards. In doing so, we aim to bridge the gap between the need for data and the desire for privacy in viticulture, ultimately benefiting all stakeholders in this intricate and cherished domain.

3.7 Services should be designed to be potentially scalable

Challenge: Information and services for agriculture are often targeting a certain set of users and crop. A number of barriers can often get in the way of expanding these to other regions, crops and types of users, limiting the useability of the service.

Solution: Services should be designed in a way that scalability is possible, and the potential extension of the product to other contexts should be considered from the early stages.

Specialised services for agriculture typically provide information for specific crops, regions and users. However, adapting services to cover different regions, crops (e.g. grapes, olive), sectors, and types of end users (i.e. users with different functions, from farmers to vineyard managers) can be a challenging task. More often than not, services do not move beyond the pilot phase, as they struggle to make the transition from prototype to transferrable and repeatable services. Scaling up services can involve a “complex, dynamical, multi-dimensional, and non-linear adaptive process”, which requires a planned and intentional approach in order to reach a wider range of users, organisations and contexts, thus having a greater impact and reach (Guentchev et al. 2023). Among other features, scalability in agriculture can involve expansion of services to wider areas, other geographic regions or crops, and inclusion of additional functions and products.

In VitiGEOSS, the scalability of services developed has been considered since the early stages of the project, since the platform was designed to allow for the incorporation of new users beyond the end-users included in the project. Expansion to other geographical areas is also possible, given the nature of the models and data sources used. In addition, expansion to other cultivars would be feasible. An example of that is the FruitLook operational service, a platform on which the VitiGEOSS platform has been based, that offers a number of indicators for other crops, such as apples. Potential cultivars that the process could be expanded to include almonds, wheat and hop. Finally, the services were developed in such a way that they can be understood and used not only by wine producers, but also by different types of users with diverse levels of expertise and technical knowledge, given that minimal training is provided.

To sum up, to ensure the scalability of information and services for agriculture, the technical aspects should be developed in a way that allows for adapting the service to include new regions and parameters. The specific user needs will differ and should be evaluated, designing the indicators as required, to align with these needs (i.e. the indicators provided for the wine sector might differ from those needed for a different crop, but can be easily adapted based on practitioners’ knowledge). The information should be presented in a manner that is understandable by users from other sectors, regions or cultivars. Finally, scalability might not only mean that all services should be scaled-up, but could involve the addition of some of the services developed (e.g. climate forecasts) to complement other existing platforms to benefit the potential users. Likewise, additional services could be added to the existing platform, as needed. These possibilities remain to be explored further.

How has VitiGEOSS worked to make scalability a possibility?

The intelligent services developed in VitiGEOSS have certain advantages that contribute to their potential scalability. These are explored in more detail below:

- **Recruitment of new users:** The VitiGEOSS platform has been developed in a way that allows for the incorporation of new users during the project’s lifetime. For this purpose, a “demo user” account has been created and distributed to interested parties during several project activities (e.g. participatory workshops). There are certain minimum requirements for new users to be incorporated into the platform, which have been described in a [document targeting the recruitment of new users](#), available in the VitiGEOSS website.

- *Geographical coverage:* While the services were originally developed and piloted at the sites of end users forming part of the project located in Italy, Spain and Portugal, the platform allows for new users from other regions and countries in Europe to be incorporated. The climate models used in the project cover a wide area across Europe, allowing for forecasts to be easily produced for other regions (falling within the area covered). Similarly, satellite data is available and can be obtained for other regions. Expansion to regions outside Europe would require further processing, however this could be a possibility in the future.
- *Expansion to other crops and sectors:* Some features available in the VitiGEOSS platform like certain crop indicators or climate forecasts, have been explored and made available to users through other platforms (e.g. FruitLook) or previous projects (e.g. MED-GOLD, S2S4E). These were further improved and explored in VitiGEOSS, providing more comprehensive services. Thus, these services can be potentially scalable to other crops and sectors by adjusting the services to the information needs of users in these crops/sectors. Nevertheless, certain parameters should be considered for certain services. For example, for scaling up crop indicators to other cultivars, some characteristics required include an extended cultivated area, preferably closed canopy, susceptibility to environmental and weather conditions, and operations depending on phenological stage.

4. Conclusions

Important insights and lessons learned during the co-production of services in the VitiGEOSS project are shared in this deliverable. These include practical aspects, such as the added value of having the different information sources and services centralised in a single platform, which reduces the time and effort of having to check different platforms or information sources. Other lessons are the need to apply a co-production approach to co-develop tailored and useful services by including the users in every step of the process, and to integrate different types of knowledge (i.e. scientific and practitioners' knowledge) in the process. Building capacity among the users is also part of the service and ensures that the information shared is actually useable and appropriately used for supporting the decisions at hand. Finally, services should be co-designed from the beginning keeping in mind their potential scalability to other regions, sectors and decision-making contexts. In this sense, a balance between open-access data and maintaining the users' privacy needs to be achieved.

This document can serve as a guide and added knowledge in the development of future services related to climate services, EO and beyond. These insights are expected to assist in the interactions among researchers (climate and data scientists), technology providers and end users, ensuring the production and delivery of clear, useful, usable, tailored and scalable information.

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